

COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOTATION PLAN 2nd VERSION

DELIVERABLE D7.5

Authors	Organization
Julia Hava	EIT Food
Maria Gomes Fernandes	New Harvest
Revised by	Organization
Deniz Koca	Lund University

Table of Contents

Table of Figures	3
Introduction	5
List of Acronyms	6
Project Overview	7
Summary of Project Objectives	7
Expected Impacts of the Project	9
Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan	10
Scope of the document	10
Key Concepts and Definitions	11
Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation	11
Different types of partnerships	13
Roles and Responsibilities, related to CDEP implementation	15
Consortium Processes & Timeframes	18
Goals, Key Messages & Channels of Communication	21
Target groups	22
Channels	1
Visibility to the EU funding- duties and rules	2
Visual identity, logo & colour palette	5
Dissemination	6
Stakeholder Engagement	11
Process of engagement	14
Exploitation	15
Steps toward the Exploitation Strategy	15
Digital Outputs Management Plan	19
Datasets and other digital outputs	19
Supporting documentation and other information	21
Persons responsible for the DOMP	22
Data protection	22
Data accessibility	22
Restrictions	23
Data security, privacy, and IPR	24
Public access	24
Costs	26
Expected updates of CDEP timeframe and partners' involvement	27

EPIC- SHIFT is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Horizon Europe. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Table of Figures

Figure 1 [The structure of overall, transversal, and specific objectives]	8
Figure 2 [Scheme illustrating the different levels of engagement with the EPIC-SHIFT project]	13
Figure 3 [Table illustrating the different levels of engagement with EPIC-SHIFT and the names of these groups]	14
Figure 4 [Table illustrating roles within the EPIC-SHIFT Consortium related to Communication and Dissemination]	17
Figure 5 [Scheme illustrating the processes through which communication and dissemination work is organised for EPIC-SHIFT team members]	18
Figure 6 [Impact for which EPIC-SHIFT aspires & Key messages designed for the EPIC-SHIFT project]	22
Figure 7	23
Figure 8 Summary of Communication and Dissemination Actions adjusted to the specific Target Groups, Table has been included in Stakeholder Engagement Plan	1
Figure 9 [Measurable results for specific project communication channels]	2
Figure 10 [Display of the European flag and funding statement]	3
Figure 11 [Media section with style guide and logo]	5
Figure 12 [Deliverables section on the project website]	6
Figure 13 [Deliverables presented in chronological order]	9
Figure 14 [Sensitive deliverables presented in chronological order]	9
Figure 15 [Milestones presented in chronological order]	10
Figure 16 [Scheme illustrating the different levels of engagement with the EPIC-SHIFT project(repeated from Figure 2)]	11
Figure 17 [Project channels and partners' channels]	14
Figure 18 [Exploitation activities proposed]	18

Project no. Grant Agreement 101181470

Project acronym: EPIC-SHIFT

Project title: Securing Holistic and Impactful Food Systems Transformation with Novel Foods based on alternative proteins

Call: HORIZON-CL6-2024-FARM2FORK-01

Start date of project: 1.11.2024

Duration: 36 months

Deliverable title: Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

Date of deliverable: 30.04.2026

Deliverable Lead Partner: EIT Food

Dissemination level: PU - Public

Introduction

This document presents the second version of the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (CDEP) for the EPIC-SHIFT project, developed within the framework of Work Package 7. The purpose of this plan is to outline the strategic approach to ensuring that project results are effectively communicated, widely disseminated, and meaningfully exploited—both during the project and beyond its duration.

The structure of this document reflects the comprehensive scope of CDEP activities. It begins with an overview of the EPIC-SHIFT project, its objectives, and expected impacts. It then defines the role of communication, dissemination, and exploitation in achieving the project's goals, and clarifies the terminology used throughout the document.

Subsequent sections describe the roles and responsibilities of different partners and groups involved in communication and dissemination activities, including the Communication and Dissemination Board (CDB) and the COMS Office. The plan also includes specific strategies for dissemination and exploitation, outlining how results will be shared with different audiences and how long-term impact will be supported.

Key messages, target groups, and selected communication channels are described in detail, together with measurable indicators of success. In addition, the document addresses the requirements for visibility of EU funding, presents the project's visual identity, and outlines the management of digital outputs and datasets in alignment with the FAIR principles¹.

Finally, an overview of deliverables and milestones is provided, followed by a description of the update timeline for future versions of this plan. This second version sets the foundation for a coordinated and impactful approach to stakeholder engagement, result sharing, and long-term knowledge use across the EPIC-SHIFT project.

List of Acronyms

Acronym Full Term

CDEP	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan
CDE	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation
COMS Office	Communication Office
CDB	Communication and Dissemination Board
DOMP	Digital Outputs Management Plan
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IP	Intellectual Property
LCA	Life-Cycle Assessment
NFAP	Proteins derived from insects, fungi, bacteria, micro- and macroalgae, and agricultural and aquacultural by-products
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor Identification
SB	Stakeholder Board
TEA	Techno-Economic Analysis
WP	Work Package

Project Overview

Summary of Project Objectives

The main objective of EPIC-SHIFT is to support the EU Protein Strategy by providing an unprecedented, independent, and robust knowledge base on the sustainability aspects—environmental, economic, and social—of novel foods based on alternative proteins (NFAP), as viable options for protein diversification for human consumption.

This will be achieved by:

- applying a multi-actor approach and engaging multiple stakeholders
- performing multidimensional and integrated impact assessments
- identifying potential challenges and opportunities posed by or to NFAP within the agri-food and bio-based sectors

EPIC-SHIFT will further build on this knowledge to develop a roadmap for the sustainable integration of NFAP into European diets—without disrupting other bio-based sectors—while ensuring food security and nutrition within a framework of just transition for all food system actors.

The structure of overall, transversal, and specific objectives is illustrated below:

Overall objective	
Promoting an independent, solid knowledge base on the sustainability aspects of NFAP as options for protein diversification for human consumption.	
Transversal Objective (TO)	Specific Objectives (SO)
<p>TO1: Alternative Proteins Knowledge Hub</p> <p>Establish a robust knowledge hub that adopts food systems thinking approach for safe and widely accessible consumption of NFAP, and to support the EU protein strategy.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Set up a stakeholder board and a science-policy-industry-society platform - Network past and ongoing projects to share best practices and identify gaps
<p>TO2: Multi-Actor Approach</p> <p>Understand risks and opportunities to formulate communication strategies tailored to specific stakeholders.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implement a quadruple helix engagement model (SMEs, academia, authorities, civil society) - Plan and conduct co-creation activities with stakeholders and projects
<p>TO3: Multidimensional & Integrated Impact</p> <p>Provide a comprehensive, unbiased, and independent study of the multidimensional and integrated impact of the development of NFAP for the food system and other bio-based sectors by adopting a systems thinking approach to integrate and model environmental principles, techno-economic considerations, and societal aspects.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Assess environmental (LCA), economic (TEA), and social (S-LCA) impacts of 7 protein types - Estimate nutritional and health benefits of NFAP - Model future scenarios for NFAP development - Define a safe and sustainable operating space for NFAP
<p>TO4: Market Studies</p> <p>Evaluate the market potential for NFAP, comprehensively understand their uptake in the food environment, and define the marketing strategies, funding and regulatory support needed for a widespread shift to their consumption in the EU.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identify market potential based on techno-functional properties and acceptance - Analyse success or failure of NFAP market launches (pricing, labelling, design) - Map scaling needs, investment dynamics, and regulatory support

Figure 1 [The structure of overall, transversal, and specific objectives]

Expected Impacts of the Project

The project is expected to generate impact across three main dimensions:

- **Scientific:** Open, improved, and comprehensive information on the environmental, economic, and social impacts of developing NFAP
- **Economic:** Enhanced competitiveness of the European NFAP industry and support for market growth
- **Societal:** Increased transparency and direct access to relevant information for NGOs and international organizations (e.g., FAO, WHO) to help accelerate the transition to sustainable, healthy, and inclusive food systems. Consumers will benefit from insights into future scenarios, nutritional profiles and health implications, and the true cost of food. The project will also identify opportunities for farmers, aquafarmers, and key actors in future NFAP value chains.

Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

The objective of EPIC-SHIFT's communication and dissemination activities, as defined in WP7, is **to maximize the impact of the project**.

The purpose of this Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan, called CDEP, is to provide a concrete strategy for communication, dissemination, and exploitation.

Scope of the document

The plan includes descriptions of target groups, key messages, media channels, as well as monitoring effective outreach (KPIs). This version sets the framework for the engagement of different partners from the consortium in communication, dissemination, and plans for the engagement of external stakeholders. The plan also establishes the framework for impact tracking and anticipates necessary adjustments in future updates.

Key Concepts and Definitions

Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation

The DCE Plan (CDEP) supports the overall project goal of promoting an independent, robust knowledge base on the sustainability aspects of NFAP as options for protein diversification for human consumption. The CDEP follows a structured approach to maximise impact. Sustainability is understood as covering environmental, economic, and social aspects. While these three elements are interconnected and often realised jointly, they serve different purposes:

- **Communication** serves to promote project activities and results to foster interest and engagement. The aim is to reach out to society as a whole and in particular to some specific audiences while demonstrating how EU funding contributes to tackling societal challenges.
- **Dissemination** serves to make the results and knowledge public (free of charge) for others to use, fulfilling the principles of Open Science. It means the public disclosure of results by appropriate means, including scientific and/or targeted conferences.
- **Exploitation** serves to make concrete use of results. It ensures that project outcomes have a lasting impact by facilitating adoption and commercialisation. This may include engaging businesses, policymakers, and EU initiatives to create opportunities for market uptake and regulatory support. Among other activities: developing, creating, manufacturing, and marketing a product or process; creating and providing a service; or engaging in standardisation activities.

The synergy between these elements ensures that EPIC-SHIFT's findings are not only widely shared but also can be effectively adopted and applied to drive sustainable protein diversification, while engaging various food system actors. For further information, you can consult the EU Commission's simple guide on the differences between dissemination, communication, and exploitation

practices.¹ , article on this matter on EU Funding Tender portal.² or the official Horizon Programme guide³ .

¹ (No date) *Europa*. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/imgs/quick-guide_diss-expl_en.pdf (Accessed: 30 April 2025).

² *What is the difference between dissemination, exploitation and communication? (2021) EU funding & tenders portal*. Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/support/faq/933?keywords=dissemination&isExactMatch=true&status=0&type=0%2C1&order=DESC&pageNumber=1&pageSize=50&sortBy=publicationDate> (Accessed: 30 April 2025).

³ (2024) *Horizon Europe Programme Guide" 2021*. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/programme-guide_horizon_en.pdf (Accessed: 30 April 2025).

Different types of partnerships

In the EPIC-SHIFT, there are diverse types of partnerships. The Project itself is implemented by twenty organizations working together in the Consortium. The EPIC-SHIFT consortium, during the project duration, will engage with numerous other initiatives and organizations outside the consortium members group.

For better understanding of the relationships of engagement and relationships between various stakeholders, they have been visualised below on the scheme.

Figure 2 [Scheme illustrating the different levels of engagement with the EPIC-SHIFT project]

Outside of the EPIC-SHIFT Consortium
Stakeholders grouped in Target Groups
EPIC-SHIFT Network
Stakeholders Board (SB)
Inside the EPIC-SHIFT Consortium
Consortium members = Consortium Partners

Figure 3 [Table illustrating the different levels of engagement with EPIC-SHIFT and the names of these groups]

In addition to the schemes above, a list of terminology related to the partnerships outside of the consortium has been prepared to assure a clear and common understanding of these processed by all involved parties and overall transparency.

To ensure clarity throughout the plan, the following terms are used with specific meanings:

- **Stakeholders** are organisations that operate in or are connected to the food system. These may include businesses, research institutions, policy bodies, or civil society actors.
- **Target groups** are specific audiences identified for communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities. While stakeholders are individual entities, target groups refer to broader categories with shared characteristics (e.g. “farmers,” “policymakers,” “investors”).
- **EPIC-SHIFT network stakeholders** are external organisations with a demonstrated interest in the project’s outcomes. These actors are drawn from various sectors and are included in a contact database maintained by the consortium.
- **Consortium members = Consortium Partners** are organisations formally participating in the EPIC-SHIFT project and responsible for delivering its tasks and results.

→ **Stakeholder Engagement** by definition is the process used by an organisation to involve relevant stakeholders for a clear purpose to achieve agreed outcomes. ⁴

→ **Stakeholder engagement in EPIC-SHIFT project** has been defined as a process of involvement of the actors outside the EPIC-SHIFT Consortium to achieve the outcomes of the project.

To develop partnerships with external stakeholders engagement process will be planned and activated.

Roles and Responsibilities, related to CDEP implementation

EIT Food has the role of the leader of Work Package 7 and Task 7.1 - Communication and Dissemination Plan and Engagement Activities in the EPIC-SHIFT project.

The Leader will work with partners and external stakeholders to lead the development and implementation of an effective communication and dissemination strategy, providing tools and materials. These tools will be developed based on information provided by the consortium members.

EIT Food will set up a Communication and Dissemination Board (CDB) to lay the foundation for communication and dissemination activities. This will include setting clear deadlines for each activity and distributing the workload among partners.

The COMS Office will be a group consisting of one representative per organization, ensuring that each partner organization is represented and can participate in the planned communication activities, as well as raise any issues to be considered in the project. Both beneficiaries and associated partners will be part of the COMS Office, and the list of the representatives will be accessible

⁴ The definition has been based on [AA1000 Stakeholder Engagement](https://www.accountability.org/standards/aa1000-stakeholder-engagement-standard/) AA1000 stakeholder engagement (no date b) Home. Available at: <https://www.accountability.org/standards/aa1000-stakeholder-engagement-standard/> (Accessed: 01 April 2025).

to all members of the consortium. It will ensure that relevant contact can be accessed easily at any time by any member of the consortium. All organizations in the consortium will select a representative for the COMS Office.

COMS Office representatives will:

- Share knowledge and materials regarding the organization they represent, and their work related to the EPIC-SHIFT project.
- Share information and essential materials needed to produce communication, dissemination, and exploitation tools and materials.

The Communication and Dissemination Board (CDB) will be the main group to discuss and agree on communication priorities and activities in the project. The members of CDB will:

- Provide substantial input throughout the project lifecycle to co-create and regularly update the Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan (CDEP).
- Conduct suitable activities to implement the plan.
- Share knowledge on the work packages they lead, as they will be in contact with Task Leaders.
- Localize communication and dissemination materials into national languages, facilitating uptake among national audiences.

To summarize, COMS Office representatives will view communication through the lens of their organization and their involvement in the project, while members of the CDB will approach communication and dissemination from the perspective of the project and the work packages they lead. The Communication and Dissemination Leader will provide the structure and facilitate the process.

EPIC- SHIFT is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Horizon Europe. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Internal Communication Channels & Feedback loop

The CDB will meet regularly online to allow discussions on plans and provide updates on the progress of work. COMS Office members will be in contact with the Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Leader online. They can be invited to CDB board meetings.

The EPIC-SHIFT Consortium has its own organisational structure serving the aims of the project and reporting obligations. In relation to communication following terminology is essential to understand the processes and how communication will be managed.

Roles within the EPIC- SHIFT Consortium	
Communication and Dissemination Leader	WP 7 Leader from EIT Food
Communication and Dissemination Board (CDB)	Plans and executes CDEP activities. Composed of WP Leaders
Communication Office (COMS Office)	Provides information and distributes information needed for CDEP activities. Composed of one representative per Beneficiary or Associated Partner

Figure 4 [Table illustrating roles within the EPIC-SHIFT Consortium related to Communication and Dissemination]

Consortium Processes & Timeframes

The processes related to CDEP implementation involve:

Figure 5 [Scheme illustrating the processes through which communication and dissemination work is organised for EPIC-SHIFT team members]

The COMS Lead, together with the CDB, proposes the tools and timeframe. For these processes, tools and procedures have been designed and they are communicated on CDB meetings with the Consortium. Consortium members are actively using project tools. Through these tools, they engage in collaborative planning, implementation (engagement), and reporting of communication activities.

Tools introduced:

Meetings: CDB meetings are a space to discuss all aspects of communication, dissemination and exploitation activities. Planning, Implementation and Reporting. Additionally to that other meetings can be organised to correspond to the needs. Such a special meeting organised by COMS Lead was for example an internal “ Special Results Sharing Session”.

Tools for Planning: Collaborative files on MS Teams, such as: Content plan including Scientific Publications Schedule,

Tools for Engagement: Engagement happens via channels (partners’ channels, project channels, activities are implemented by different members of the consortium. There can be several channels of implementation and several partners involved. Key for collaborations is to make sure that plans are shared in advance and implemented in a way that is coherent with the project objectives and the CDEP, including visual identity and visibility of EU

EPIC- SHIFT is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Horizon Europe. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

funding. It is key to inform COMS Lead, Project Coordinator and CDB members in advance about planned engagement to assure tools used are adequate.

Tools for Internal Reporting: The reporting tools in the project assure the collection of data on implemented activities.

Continuous reporting. The main tool at the moment is the Communication Activities Continuous Reporting Survey, together with folders designated for attachments . Additional data for reporting can be requested by the COMS Lead and the Project Coordinator to ensure that all necessary data are provided to the Funding Agency as part of continuous and mid-term reporting.

Tools for Mid-Term Reporting: Here collaborative files are being used.

Planning and feedback timeframe:

CDB meetings are organised on a regular basis. Partners' plans for communication and stakeholder engagement activities, as well as upcoming results of work, should be shared as early as possible with the consortium. Consortium members are invited to provide feedback on key processes, documents, or proposed approaches. Collaborative discussion is encouraged during CDB meetings; however, details should be provided in written form before the CDB or shortly after, via collaborative files.

Feedback on tools and documents should ideally be submitted ahead of the upcoming CDB meeting so that it can be discussed during the meeting, if needed. In all cases, feedback should be provided before the deadline of the relevant activity in order to ensure that project timelines are respected.

Partners are encouraged to propose alternative solutions where they believe there is a more effective way of implementing a given activity, or to suggest corrections to documents or planned actions. If they identify an important error or scientific incoherence, they should communicate it, as the project aims to assure the highest quality standards. All feedback and proposed changes are welcome and will be considered, provided they are shared within a reasonable timeframe.

The applicable timeframe for feedback depends on the frequency of meetings and the period available between them. As a general guideline, this timeframe may be up to 30 days; however, it may be shorter in cases where deadlines are tight, for example during reporting periods.

Press release

In the case of a press release, the need for it should be communicated well in advance to the COMS Lead. To support the timely identification of opportunities and to build momentum for press releases, a Scientific Publications Schedule has been introduced as an additional section of the content plan.

Reporting timeframe

The reporting timeframe depends on the specificity of reporting requirements. If it is not a mid-term reporting period, the standard timeframe for reporting a communication activity is within 30 days after delivery. Proof of delivery is required and should be stored by the partner and shared as an attachment on MS Teams. The aim is to ensure that all necessary data are available for the CDB team when needed.

Goals, Key Messages & Channels of Communication

The key messages listed below were developed by the WP7 Leader in collaboration with the Communication and Dissemination Board. These messages will be further refined following the stakeholder mapping activities, which aim to provide a deeper understanding of the needs and perspectives of different target groups. The goals outlined below reflect the intended impact of the EPIC-SHIFT project. For each goal, up to five core key messages have been proposed. The key messages below have been updated based on the Stakeholder Engagement Plan.

Goal	Key Messages
<p>Promote stronger collaboration between academia and industry</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaboration between academia and industry leads to impactful research. • Solving the climate crisis and the need for a resilient food system requires cross-sector cooperation. • EPIC-SHIFT encourages multidisciplinary collaboration. • Join the EPIC-SHIFT network to contribute and connect. • Use your channels; we provide the knowledge—let’s reach audiences together • we provide the evidence
<p>Support open, comprehensive access to knowledge on the environmental, economic, and social impacts of NFAP</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We promote transparency as a basis for just food system transformation. • Impact analysis results will be shared openly. • Research findings and models will be disseminated early under open science principles.
<p>Highlight the competitiveness of the European NFAP sector and support market growth</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Our findings contribute to a stronger, more competitive EU protein sector. • EPIC-SHIFT helps shape EU policy for sustainable protein systems. • We are building a central knowledge hub for alternative proteins.

<p>Provide accessible information to NGOs and international organisations (e.g. FAO, WHO)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Results are made available via the project website. • Data is shared via open access platforms for broad public use.
<p>Empower consumers with information on food futures and full-cost impacts</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Novel foods offer alternatives within healthy diets. • Specific NFAP products suit particular consumer needs. • Protein sources vary in CO₂ impact—some are significantly lower. • We support informed food choices by showing the true cost. • Consumers should be mindful when adopting novel foods.
<p>Inform farmers, aquafarmers, and actors in future NFAP value chains</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We identify the most promising scale-up opportunities and their needs. • Actionable information will be shared (e.g. market entry points, prices). • Our findings guide policy and practice for producers and value chain actors.

Figure 6 [Impact for which EPIC-SHIFT aspires & Key messages designed for the EPIC-SHIFT project]

Target groups

The table below presents description of each target group. For each target group approach to be applied has been defined.

No	Target Group	Description & approach to be applied
	<p>Researchers</p>	<p>Researchers from various disciplines—such as food systems, food science, climate research, marketing, and economics—will be targeted. The results of EPIC-SHIFT will be published as soon as they become available to ensure timely exploitation across interconnected fields.</p>
	<p>NFAP Producers</p>	<p>Companies (both SMEs and larger groups) already established or entering the market during EPIC-SHIFT implementation will be kept informed. This includes the provision of knowledge on production impact, marketing strategies, consumer perspectives, and recommendations for business scale-up.</p>

EPIC-SHIFT is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Horizon Europe. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

	Food Industry Actors & Connected Services	Food distributors, food service providers, retailers, and technology suppliers will receive market projections, marketing strategies, and consumer acceptance data to support the uptake of NFAP and the growth of the market.
	Investors	Investment needs and recommendations for investment schemes will be shared with investors to help identify funding opportunities that can enhance EU competitiveness in the long term.
	Farmers	Farmers and aquafarmers will be engaged in dialogue and provided with information on the impacts of their current practices compared to NFAP production. Opportunities and alternative business models to sustainably increase their income will also be highlighted.
	Decision and Policy-Makers	Research findings from EPIC-SHIFT will be disseminated to policy- and decision-makers through dedicated meetings, and publications offering a decision-support tool for evidence-based policymaking.
	Consumers	Consumers will be reached through social media and media articles. These communications will offer transparent information on the nutritional value, safety, sustainability impact, and taste of NFAP—key factors influencing purchasing decisions.

Figure 7 [Target Group with Description & approach to be applied]

EPIC- SHIFT is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Horizon Europe. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Target Group	Language	Format	Channels	Content
Researchers	scientific language	more complex information scientific articles	scientific publications scientific conferences and events	evidence-based results of the project, impact assessments, models and methodologies
NFAP Producers	vulgarized fact - based info	short, practical info case studies/ good examples/success stories technical reports funding proposals	entrepreneurial meetings	market predictions, pricing perspectives, production impacts, marketing strategies, consumer perspectives, and recommendations for business scale-up.
Industry Actors	vulgarized fact - based info	short, practical info ready to use results of research	industry events	product prototypes, LCA topline results, value proposition of NFAP, market projections, marketing strategies, and consumer acceptance data to support the uptake of NFAP and the growth of the market.
Investors	vulgarized on technical feasibility impartial/unbiased language	fact-based info format easy to use in practice legitimizing the category collecting feedback and endorsing some in our conclusions	conferences (New FOOD Paradigm Conference)	consumer and market readiness, market projections, information on deal flows, funding opportunities, recommendations for investment schemes
Farmers	clear, unbiased language	practical, successful stories, case studies of new business opportunities to farmers prototypes/business models applicable and compliant with regulations easy to implement	farmer newspapers, magazines, podcasts farmer to farmer farmer advisers field events	information on supply demand, on funding opportunities supporting the transition to NFAP production
Decision and Policy-Makers	more technocratic language	evidence-based info policy papers	roundtables/seminars/webinars	NFAP impacts, policy recommendations
Consumers	easy language, consistent terminology	transparent, short info media articles news on social media	general media ambassadors/influencers, consumer tastings	information on the nutritional value, safety, sustainability impact, and taste of NFAP—key factors influencing purchasing decisions.

Figure 8 [Summary of the Format, Language and Channels adjusted to the specific Target Groups]

Channels

For effective communication, dissemination, and exploitation, five channels have been identified, with measurable results expected to be achieved. Detailed information is provided in the table below.

Communication channel	Measurable result
<p><u>Visual identity and Project website:</u></p> <p>A visual identity for the project will be created, including at least the logo and templates for documents and presentations. A dedicated website will be created by EIT Food to communicate the project and its results. It will enable effective communication between the project and external stakeholders, providing information on the project, the consortium, stakeholders, as well as project activities and results. Links to the project website will be included on all partners' websites.</p>	<p>Visual identity of the project - established</p> <p>website online</p> <p>≥ 5,000 visits on the website</p>
<p><u>Social media:</u></p> <p>Relevant information will be distributed on LinkedIn through a dedicated project page. This will serve as a tool to report on unfolding developments throughout the project. Posts will include, among others:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facts on main findings • Insights from conferences and meetings • Updates on milestone achievements • Information about forthcoming events • Curiosity-driven content related to project topics (e.g. educational posts) <p>More categories of information may be identified in future versions of this document.</p>	<p>≥ 36 posts accumulated during the whole duration of the project</p> <p>≥ 750 followers</p> <p>(250 until November 2025)</p> <p>500 until November 2026</p> <p>750 until November 2027)</p>
<p><u>Media:</u></p> <p>Press releases will be published whenever a key milestone is achieved. Selected online industry media, journals, and blogs will be used. Partners will also utilize EC tools to inform about dedicated project outcomes for example via Horizon Magazine, Research EU magazine, and CORDIS.</p>	<p>≥ 3 international press releases</p> <p>≥ 5 dedicated publications</p> <p>Minimum:</p>

	<p>1 international PR until November 2025, 1 publication</p> <p>1 international PR until December 2026,</p> <p>1 international PR until November 2027, 5 publications</p>
<p><u>Newsletters:</u></p> <p>An informative e-newsletter will be produced regularly, at least every 6 months and during key communication moments with details of the project's activities/outcomes/results, to be sent out to the project mailing database and by project partners to relevant stakeholders from their mailing database in compliance with GDPR. New audiences will be able to subscribe to the newsletter on the project's website.</p> <p>An informative e-newsletter will be produced regularly, every 6 months and during key communication moments, with details on the project's activities, outcomes, and results. This will be sent out to the project mailing database and by project partners to relevant stakeholders from their mailing database, in compliance with GDPR. New audiences can subscribe to the newsletter via the project's website.</p>	<p>≥ 6 newsletters distributed until the end of the project</p> <p>On average ≥ 2/ year</p> <p>4 Newsletters until January 2027</p> <p>2 Newsletters until November 2027</p>
<p><u>Partners channels and networks:</u></p> <p>EPIC-SHIFT partners will use all their communication channels (website, social networks), relevant networks and memberships to spread the progress of activities and project results, to help raise awareness of the project and engage with relevant stakeholders.</p>	<p>≥ 800 users redirected to EPIC- SHIFT website</p> <p>250 users redirected until November 2025,</p> <p>500 users redirected until November 2026</p> <p>600 users redirected until November 2027</p>

Figure 9 [Measurable results for specific project communication channels]

Visibility to the EU funding- duties and rules

All beneficiaries of the project must ensure visibility of EU funding. The most important duties and rules related to the presentation of EU support are listed below. The information is based on Article 17 of the Grant Agreement on Communication, Dissemination, and Visibility.

EPIC- SHIFT is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Horizon Europe. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

European Flag and Funding Statement

Unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority, communication activities of the beneficiaries related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information materials, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major results funded by the grant must acknowledge the EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate):

Figure 10 [Display of the European flag and funding statement]

The emblem must remain distinct and separate and cannot be modified by adding other visual marks, brands, or text. Apart from the emblem, no other visual identity or logo may be used to highlight the EU support. When displayed in association with other logos (e.g. of beneficiaries or sponsors), the emblem must be displayed at least as prominently and visibly as the other logos.

Quality of information & Disclaimer

Any communication or dissemination activity related to the action must use factually accurate information. If certain information was not factually accurate (e.g. new results obtained in a project disprove earlier information given about preliminary results), the beneficiaries must take any appropriate and immediate steps to correct the inaccurate information.

Communication and dissemination materials must indicate the following disclaimer (translated into local languages where appropriate):

Funding statement: Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or REA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

EPIC- SHIFT is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Horizon Europe. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Major Media Impact

Major media impact must be communicated with the Agency. If such an action is planned, the Communication WP Leader must be informed, and the Project Coordinator must be informed to decide if such an action needs to be communicated with the Agency. The most appropriate space to communicate the plan for such an action will be the meeting of the Communication and Dissemination Board.

Visual identity, logo & colour palette

Figure 11 [Media section with style guide and logo

]

The WP7 Leader has prepared a visual identity, logo, and colour palette for the project to ensure a coherent visual identity for EPIC-SHIFT.

Guidelines have been shared with all members of the consortium. A full version of the Style Guide is available on the project website under the Media Page, where it can be downloaded by project partners and all interested parties. Link: <https://epic-shift.eu/media/>

Dissemination

As defined in the Key Concepts and Definitions section of this document, dissemination serves to make the results and knowledge public for others to use, fulfilling the value of Open Science. Below, we present how dissemination has been planned to best fulfil the objective of public access to knowledge, the parties involved in the dissemination process, and dedicated space for results to be easily accessed by interested parties.

In the case of the EPIC-SHIFT project, the objective of public access will be achieved by ensuring that most deliverables can be accessed publicly online.

Roles and Responsibilities in Dissemination

Members of the project consortium prepare deliverables and submit them to the project coordinator. Once the deliverable passes the review by ULUND, it is considered ready for publishing. The project coordinator and the respective organization responsible for the specific deliverable will inform the WP7 Leader. The WP7 Leader can upload the file to the website or upload the file themselves.

The Communication and Dissemination Leader has planned a dedicated section on the website to facilitate easy access to deliverables. The deliverables can be accessed on the project website, specially designated for that purpose. Link: <https://epic-shift.eu/results/>

Figure 12 [Deliverables section on the project website]

Target groups identified for dissemination activities are matching those

EPIC- SHIFT is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Horizon Europe. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

identified for communication. Seven general target groups have been pre-identified in the Grant Agreement for these purposes. They will be described in further sections of this document. These target groups will be directed to the project website on various occasions and through selected channels.

Milestones & Deliverables

Project milestones and deliverables outlined in the Grant Agreement will serve as reference points for identifying key moments throughout the project. They will be used to align communication and dissemination efforts, ensuring strategic and timely outreach.

Thirty deliverables and ten milestones have been listed in the Grant Agreement. Twenty-seven deliverables are planned to be disseminated publicly. These twenty-seven deliverables will be available on the project website. Among the deliverables, three will be internal project documents that ensure effective and ethical project implementation and will not be disseminated publicly. Their dissemination level has been marked in the GA as "sensitive."

The tables below provide an overview of the deliverables and milestones in chronological order.

All project deliverables are listed in the table below. Those with a white background are sensitive and will not be disseminated publicly.

Deliverables in chronological order

No.	Deliverable Name	WP N ^o	Partner	Type	Due Date (month)
1	OEI - Requirement No. 1	WP8	ULUND	ETHICS	1
2	Project website	WP7	EIT FOOD	DEC — Websites, patent filings, videos,	4
3	First version of Data management plan (DMP)	WP1	ULUND	DMP — Data Management Plan	6
4	First version of Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan	WP7	EIT FOOD	R — Document, report	6

5	First version of Watch Platform	WP2	SHAKE-UP	R — Document, report	9
6	First version of Food systems interactive visualisation tool	WP2	ULUND	DEM — Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	12
7	Recommendations for Novel Foods regulatory approval process	WP5	ATOVA	R — Document, report	12
8	NFAP Market projections according to techno-functional properties	WP3	CTIC CITA	R — Document, report	15
9	Second version of Data management plan (DMP)	WP1	ULUND	DMP — Data Management Plan	18
10	Second Report of Ethical Advisor	WP1	ULUND	R — Document, report	18
11	Second version of Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan	WP7	EIT FOOD	R — Document, report	18
12	Nutritional and health impacts of NFAP in diets	WP5	UOXF	R — Document, report	20
13	Optimal NFAP marketing strategies	WP3	ACG-RC	R — Document, report	24
14	Pricing perspectives of NFAP	WP3	UOXF	R — Document, report	24
15	Opportunities and challenges for farmers and aquafarmers	WP5	DLG	R — Document, report	24
16	LCA of NFAP	WP4	UH	R — Document, report	28
17	TEA of NFAP	WP4	DTU	R — Document, report	28
18	S-LCA of NFAP	WP4	ECOINNOVAZIONE	R — Document, report	28
19	Second version of Food systems interactive visualisation tool	WP2	ULUND	DEM — Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	30
20	Recommendations for investments in NFAP	WP3	SHAKE-UP	R — Document, report	30
21	Market adoption report	WP5	CTIC CITA	R — Document, report	30
22	Policy Recommendations	WP7	SAFE	R — Document, report	33
23	Systems modelling of NFAP impact	WP6	ULUND	R — Document, report	34

EPIC- SHIFT is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Horizon Europe. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

24	Dietary challenges and opportunities of NFAP	WP6	UOXF	R — Document, report	34
26	Third version of Data management plan (DMP)	WP1	ULUND	DMP — Data Management Plan	36
27	Second Report of Ethical Advisor	WP1	ULUND	R — Document, report	36
28	Second version of Watch Platform	WP2	SHAKE-UP	R — Document, report	36
29	White paper harnessing NFAP impact to further societal goals	WP6	ULUND	R — Document, report	36
30	Exploitation strategy and funding watch	WP7	EIT FOOD	R — Document, report	36

Figure 13 [Deliverables presented in chronological order]

Sensitive Deliverables

Nº	Deliverable Name	Deliverable Nº	WP Nº	Partner	Type	Due Date (Month)
1	OEI - Requirement No. 1	D8.1	WP8	ULUND	ETHICS	1
2	First Report of Ethical Advisor	D1.4	WP1	ULUND	ETHICS	18
3	Second Report of Ethical Advisor	D1.5	WP1	ULUND	ETHICS	36

Figure 14 [Sensitive deliverables presented in chronological order]

Milestones

Nº	Milestone name	WP Nº	Partner	Due date (month)
1.	Key stakeholders are mapped and engaged and DCE activities are running	WP2, WP7	EIT FOOD	6
2.	Knowledge gathered from other relevant projects is shared within EPIC-SHIFT (Internal report supported by a webinar (T2.2))	WP2	CTIC CITA	6

EPIC- SHIFT is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Horizon Europe. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

3.	Set of samples per protein type have been chosen and acquired/provided	WP3	CTIC CITA	8
4.	Major environmental and socio- economic issues, policy priorities, potential benefits, and risks as well as challenges, barriers, and gaps for the development of NFAP are identified	WP2	ULUND	9
5.	Specific directions obtained from stakeholders and baseline analysis performed	WP4, WP2	UH	9
6.	Insights from content analysis and plans for assessment of brand performance defined	WP3	ACG-RC	12
7.	Conceptual models of NFAP production at scale generated	WP4	DTU	14
8.	Preliminary results regarding market potential, environmental, social, economic, regulatory assessments have been collected from WP2- WP5	WP5, WP4, WP3, WP6, WP2	ULUND	18
9.	Effective channels and dynamics of co- creation process and policy dialogue have been successfully established	WP7	9 - EIT FOOD	30

Figure 15 [Milestones presented in chronological order]

Stakeholder Engagement

The stakeholders can be analysed not only by their role in the food system but also by their level of engagement in EPIC SHIFT. In the case of EPIC SHIFT project, the prioritization of engagement led to the identification of **engagement levels**. This is visualised in the graph below. Although it is presented in the *Key Concepts* chapter, it is repeated here to provide further detail

Figure 16 [Scheme illustrating the different levels of engagement with the EPIC-SHIFT project(repeated from Figure 2)]

Stakeholders (any) - The widest circle represents all stakeholders who will be reached with information on EPIC SHIFT project. They are simply **recipients of information** on the project, and no action is required from them. It is the lowest level of engagement performing informative function of engagement– diffusion of information/knowledge.

EPIC SHIFT network – middle circle encompasses stakeholders who have interest in EPIC SHIFT project and **have joined the network**. In this way they will be regularly informed about the progress in the EPIC SHIFT implementation and about its results. EPIC SHIFT network also includes the stakeholders that are important from the point of view of objectives and

EPIC- SHIFT is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Horizon Europe. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

implementation of EPIC SHIFT project. They may have knowledge, expertise that the partners do not have or allow to reach the stakeholders we have little access to. Therefore, it is in the interest of the partners to keep them interested in the project and make sure they are informed about its progress and results.

They are the stakeholders, which are **key players in novel food system**, and which are **either targeted by communication and dissemination activities or actively involved in the projects' implementation activities**. The key stakeholders have been identified during the stakeholders mapping process. EPIC-SHIFT Consortium members will make active efforts to promote stakeholder network and invite entities to become part of it.

The Stakeholder's Board is the body envisaged in the project proposal. The composition of Stakeholder's Board should also consider **inclusivity principle** and represent all stakeholder types from four fields: academia, industry, civil society and government in line with quadruple helix model. The special attention should be given to representatives of the civil society, which are not directly involved in the project implementation but are important from the point of view of meeting objectives of the project and learning different perspectives on the sustainability issues (e.g. organisation active in the field of climate change, food diversity, environment protection).

As the Stakeholder Board represents the closest and most structured form of engagement within the project, its activation will take place once other engagement processes are already in operation. In particular, this includes the engagement of EPIC-SHIFT within existing spaces of interaction and collaboration that are already established.

Existing spaces of engagement include ongoing collaborations between relevant entities such as Horizon for Proteins Cluster. The objective of supporting exploitation activities is particularly important and differentiates the Stakeholder Board from other forms of engagement. For this reason, the activation and operation of the Stakeholder Board will be most effective once a greater number of project results and deliverables are available, as this will allow for a more targeted selection of members that better suits the project objectives and specific needs.

The composition of the Stakeholder Board is intended to best support the project objectives. As such, its final composition may differ from that initially described in the proposal, in order to better align with the evolving requirements and main objectives of the project.

Process of engagement

The stakeholders are engaged in the EPIC SHIFT project via different channels. The channels provided for in EPIC SHIFT and by partners allow to reach a wide range of stakeholders.

Figure 17 [Project channels and partners' channels]

Exploitation

As defined in the *Key Concepts* section, exploitation refers to the concrete use of project results. It ensures that project outcomes have a lasting impact by supporting their adoption and potential commercialization.

Exploitation activities in EPIC-SHIFT are designed to ensure that the knowledge, tools, and outcomes generated by the project are meaningfully used by a wide range of stakeholders long after the project ends. This will be achieved by strengthening connections between the consortium and key partners across research, policy, and the food system.

The exploitation strategy (D7.4), part of Task 7.5, is coordinated by EIT Food and supported by ULUND, SHAKE-UP FACTORY, and NH. An initial exploitation plan is included in this second version of the Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan, while a more detailed strategy will be delivered as Deliverable D7.4 by Month 36.

Steps toward the Exploitation Strategy

To ensure that project results are adopted and sustained beyond the lifetime of EPIC-SHIFT, the following steps will be implemented:

a) Develop Standards for Interoperability

Work with research, policy, and industry stakeholders to define and promote interoperable formats and frameworks, enabling the integration and reuse of project outputs across relevant domains.

b) Internal and External Stakeholder Engagement

Identify key exploitable results early and actively involve both internal consortium partners and external actors in shaping their use. Engagement efforts will target stakeholders in policy, business, civil society, and academia to co-create pathways for uptake and relevance.

c) Funding Watch and Synergy Building

Establish a Funding Watch to monitor and connect with ongoing and upcoming funding and investment opportunities at EU, national, and international levels. Targeted programmes include:

- European Fund for Strategic Investments
- EU Smart Specialisation Strategies
- Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking (CBE-JU) Open Calls
- EIT Food Open Innovation Calls
- Canadian Strategic Innovation Fund (SIF)

This will support follow-up initiatives that build on EPIC-SHIFT's results and increase long-term sustainability.

The final version of the exploitation strategy (Deliverable D7.4) will present a structured plan for the long-term exploitation of outcomes, outlining actions extending up to four years beyond project completion.

Stakeholder Board

To support long-term uptake, EPIC-SHIFT will establish a **Stakeholder Board (SB)** composed of organisations representing various stakeholder groups. An initial list of members is proposed in the Grant Agreement. The SB will:

- Support targeted exploitation of results
- Advise the consortium on reaching target groups
- Act as ambassadors for key outcomes

Membership procedures and terms of cooperation will be confirmed at the General Assembly, ensuring transparent and inclusive engagement.

The table below presents an initial list of exploitable results, along with their target stakeholders and strategies for future exploitation activities. These proposals may be modified and will be further developed as deeper work on exploitation plan is carried out.

Result	Target Stakeholder Type	Delivery Month	Result Type / Value	Exploitation Strategy
Watch Platform (D2.1, D2.3)	Science-policy actors, EIT Food Protein Diversification Think Tank	9	Digital platform for monitoring trends	To be possibly integrated into the EIT Food Think Tank to inform data-driven dialogue and guide protein diversification initiatives or in the Biotech Alliance
NFAP Market Growth Projections (D3.1)	NFAP producers, investors, supply chain	15	Forecasting tool / business intelligence	Used by stakeholders to guide investment, plan infrastructure, and align supply chain strategies with future demand.
Recommendations for Novel Foods Regulatory Approval Process (D5.1)	EFSA	18	Policy recommendation	Promoted to EFSA and other regulators to improve the responsiveness and efficiency of the novel food approval process.
Marketing Strategies (D3.2)	NFAP producers, supply chain actors	20	Market uptake strategy	Applied to shape favourable food environments and increase NFAP consumer acceptance and market entry.
Food Systems Visualisation Tool (D2.2)	Researchers, NGOs, policymakers (e.g. Knowledge Centre for Global Food and Nutrition Security)	22	Scenario tool	Promoted for use in multi-stakeholder scenario planning and food system transformation initiatives.

Pricing Perspectives (D3.3)	Policymakers, investors, NFAP developers	24	Economic policy insight	Used to stimulate policy discussions on fair pricing, true cost accounting, and public funding strategies for NFAP.
Opportunities for Farmers and Aquafarmers (D5.3)	EIP-AGRI Operational Groups, farmers, aquafarmers, producer networks	30	Stakeholder report identifying leverage points for NFAP integration	Promoted through farmer networks and EIP-AGRI to support integration of primary producers into NFAP value chains. Identifies business opportunities and systemic enablers to increase farmer and aquafarmer participation.
System Dynamics Model (D6.1)	Researchers, NGOs, policymakers	33	Analytical tool	Used in multi-actor dialogues to simulate policy impacts and guide food systems planning.
Report on Dietary Challenges & Opportunities (D6.2)	Researchers, NGOs, policymakers	34	Policy-oriented report	Disseminated to support informed decision-making on sustainable dietary transitions.
White Paper on NFAP (D6.3)	Policymakers (EFSA, DG AGRI, FAO)	36	Policy briefing / roadmap	Used in EU and international working groups to influence protein diversification policies.

Figure 18 [Exploitation activities proposed]

Digital Outputs Management Plan

The EPIC-SHIFT project is grounded in the principles of transparency and open science, with a strong commitment to promoting data sharing across various aspects of alternative protein sources (NFAP; proteins derived from insect, fungi, bacteria, micro and macro algae and agriculture and aquaculture by-products). This effort aims to enhance public understanding, support informed policymaking, and enrich scientific dialogue around NFAP.

To achieve this, the project will facilitate data exchange both within the consortium and with a broader network of external stakeholders. The ultimate objective is to establish EPIC-SHIFT as a trusted, impartial source of information – serving researchers, policymakers, and the general public throughout the project's lifespan and beyond.

Supporting this commitment, the Digital Outputs Management Plan (DOMP) serves as a dynamic companion to the Data Management Plan (DMP). It outlines the types of data and information the project will generate, as well as strategies for collection, storage, and public access.

The Data Management Plan (DMP) for this project is a separate guidance document that is regularly updated. The most recent version is the second version, which serves as the reference for data management aspects, including the allocation of resources, data security, and ethics.

Datasets and other digital outputs

EPIC-SHIFT is expected to generate a diverse array of datasets and digital outputs, aligned with the thematic focus of Work Packages 2 through 7. These

outputs generally fall into three broad categories: technical data, socio-economic data, and analytical modelling data. Technical data will include scientific information related to the components, processes, and final products of alternative proteins sources and technologies. This data will be valuable to scientists and engineers, encompassing the full production cycle—from cell sourcing to final product—and including nutrition and safety analytics to assess potential impacts on consumer health. Sources for this data will include both experimental research carried out by consortium members and, where possible, data shared by external stakeholders.

Socio-economic data will focus on the broader context of implementing alternative protein sources in food systems. This will cover topics such as supply chains, consumer perspectives, potential business models, regulatory frameworks (including safety and labelling policies), and the potential impact on stakeholders in the existing food value chain. These insights will be informed by literature reviews as well as stakeholder engagement activities such as workshops conducted by consortium partners and supplemented, when possible, by contributions from outside the consortium.

Analytical modelling data will involve computational assessments using large datasets to explore both scientific and socio-economic dimensions of NFAP. This will include techno-economic analyses (TEAs) and life cycle assessments (LCAs) that help define key parameters for developing and scaling alternative protein sources and technologies across various production and distribution models. These datasets will be sourced from within the consortium or shared by external partners when feasible.

Given the range of subjects covered, the data produced will include both qualitative and quantitative formats, presented in digital, textual, visual, or multimedia forms. While individual partners may develop dedicated databases for specific topics, efforts will be made to integrate and consolidate these datasets within relevant work packages or under a consortium-wide data structure.

Supporting documentation and other information

What supporting documentation, or other information, such as metadata, are planned to make data and digital outputs publicly accessible and to support their longer-term reuse?

To ensure the long-term accessibility and reusability of data and digital outputs, EPIC-SHIFT will follow the FAIR principles—Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse—in line with best practices in Open Science. All data will be accompanied by relevant metadata and clearly defined keywords to enhance discoverability for a range of users. The project will also make use of permanent identifiers, such as Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) for publications and ORCIDs for authors, to support citation and attribution.

Research findings will be shared regularly over the course of the project, with a strong emphasis on publishing in peer-reviewed journals that offer open access options whenever possible. Additionally, open repositories such as ZENODO and BioRxiv will be used to ensure the continued availability of publications and preprints, including those from high-impact journals that may not offer open access. Multiple repositories may be used depending on the nature of the material, and partners may also develop their own platforms to host relevant publications and data.

Datasets will be released either upon publication of associated research or according to timelines established by the consortium or agreed upon with external collaborators—particularly when the data involves confidential or proprietary information. The processes for data storage, access, and protection are further detailed in the project's Data Management Plan (DMP), which provides comprehensive guidance on how these resources will be curated and maintained over time.

Persons responsible for the DOMP

Which members are responsible for developing, implementing, overseeing, and updating the DOMP?

Individual work packages and task leaders are responsible for the appropriate development and implementation of data collection, storage, and sharing activities according to DMP and DOMP for data generated under their oversight.

The task lead for WP7, task 7.4 (New Harvest-NL), is responsible for developing, overseeing, and updating the DOMP, in conjunction/alignment with updates to the DMP that are implemented and overseen by the Project Coordinator (ULUND) and project DPO.

Data protection

How will data and digital outputs be managed during the project to protect their long-term value?

See the DMP point regarding (Data Security) for details. More detailed descriptions will be added to the DOMP as platforms are developed and defined for data storage, handling, and output.

Data accessibility

How and by which members will data and other digital outputs be managed after the project ends to ensure long-term accessibility?

Data is planned to be stored for at least 5 years after the end of the project. The DOMP will be updated to identify relevant partners with sufficient

infrastructure and resources to maintain archival platforms. The leader of WP7, task 7.4, (New Harvest-NL) in conjunction with the Project Coordinator (ULUND) will work to ensure publications and data are archived for long-term storage in a certified repository.

Restrictions

What restrictions could be placed on how data and digital outputs can be accessed or reused?

Technical data may contain information that is sensitive, whether confidential or proprietary. Restrictions on how such data from consortium partners can be accessed and reused, especially by persons/entities outside the consortium/project will be guided by project contract agreements. For data shared by external persons/entities, restrictions will be guided by bilateral agreements between project partners and data sharers.

Socio-economic data, especially those involving personal questionnaires or reporting (including internal to the project), may contain sensitive information for persons/entities. A detailed description of how such information will be managed can be found in section Ethics of the DMP. Briefly, EPIC-SHIFT will comply with Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and the Council of 26.04.2016 (known as GDPR, the general data protection regulation), as well as Directive 2002/58/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 July 2002. Such data protections may also fall under the national legislation of specific partners. Analytical models may employ sensitive data of a technical and/or personal nature. Restrictions on storage, handling, and access will be guided by the relevant agreements and/or regulations mentioned above. Informed consent and issues related to long-term storage will be addressed before data collection. To protect sensitive data, the handling, storage, and retrieval (whether for internal or public use) may involve levels of anonymization, regarding data or sources of data.

Data security, privacy, and IPR

Measures to protect data security, privacy, and intellectual property (IP) rights within EPIC-SHIFT are clearly defined and will be implemented throughout the project. The management of intellectual property rights for data generated or shared by consortium members is governed by the Consortium Agreement, which outlines responsibilities and terms of use. For data provided by external collaborators, appropriate protections and terms will be established through bilateral agreements with the relevant consortium partners.

In keeping with the project's commitment to open science, research findings and associated datasets are expected to be made publicly accessible, with open access publishing as the standard. When appropriate, Creative Commons (CC) licenses will be applied to ensure that data and digital outputs can be reused in a way that respects authorship and legal rights. These licenses will support the ethical reuse of materials while safeguarding the interests of data providers, including for any derivative works that may arise from the project's outputs.

In general, AI assistants other than built-in tools are not permitted to operate within the MS Teams project workspace of EPIC-SHIFT. AI tools may be used for tasks related to elements developed outside the common project space (e.g. graphic design). AI tools must not be used to process or handle sensitive project data.

Public access

What publicly accessible mechanisms/documentation are planned to support long term discoverability and reuse of the data and digital outputs?

The EPIC-SHIFT website (<https://epic-shift.eu/>) will serve as the primary hub for sharing project-related information with the public. It will provide regular updates on key activities, including conference dates and presentations, upcoming workshops, research results, blogs offering informal insights on relevant topics, as well as access to publications such as pre-prints, peer-reviewed journal articles, and links to permanent repositories. The site will also feature information on expected milestones and deliverables to keep stakeholders informed of project progress.

As the project evolves, the Digital Outputs Management Plan (DOMP) is being updated to include any additional online platforms used for sharing information or data, following the same principles as the EPIC-SHIFT website. In line with the project's commitment to open science, publications will be made available through open access whenever possible, with pre-prints shared in public repositories if open-access publication in high-impact journals is not feasible. The use of Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs), ORCIDs, carefully selected keywords, and detailed metadata for both publications and datasets will follow the guidance laid out in the most up to date version of Data Management Plan (DMP), ensuring that outputs are easily discoverable, citable, and reusable.

In this second version of the plan, following the Open Science Workshop conducted with the project consortium, an additional tool supporting public access has been set up since the first CDEP and DOMP.

This is the EPIC-SHIFT Zenodo Community(<https://zenodo.org/communities/epic-shift/>), where all consortium members have their profiles, and public deliverables of interest to a broader audience will be shared as part of the EPIC-SHIFT Community.

The CDEP and DMP do not need to be shared within the Zenodo Community. It is sufficient for these documents to be published on the project website.

The project website remains the central hub for public access, while Zenodo serves as a complementary tool that strengthens actions towards public access, particularly within the scientific community.

Costs

How are the costs necessary to ensure long-term accessibility of data and digital outputs being secured?

As outlined in the Data Management Plan (DMP), each consortium partner will be responsible for covering the costs associated with the curation and preservation of the data they generate, manage, or store. In cases where long-term data platforms are developed to host collective datasets—those that span multiple tasks or reflect the project as a whole and cannot be attributed to a single partner—the Digital Outputs Management Plan (DOMP) will be updated to reflect the associated costs and responsibilities for maintaining those shared resources.

Expected updates of CDEP timeframe and partners' involvement

The CDEP (Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan) is a living document that will evolve based on project progress and stakeholder feedback. Key updates in future versions include the second and third versions.

The third version will include the exploitation plan. The final version of the CDEP must include the dissemination and exploitation activities that the beneficiaries plan to implement for up to four years after the end of the project.

Timeframe and involvement of partners

M6 – First version of the CDEP to be published (deliverable).

M7 – M16 – Gathering of information regarding target groups and stakeholders from the consortium. Formulation of the strategy for involving stakeholders identified during the stakeholder mapping (WP2). Discussion of possibilities and planning of stakeholder involvement.

M7 – M16 – Review of updates in the DOMP and incorporation into the updated CDEP.

M15 – M17 – Inclusion of the stakeholder involvement plan within the overall project plans.

M16 – M17 – Opportunity for the CDB to provide comments and proposals during this period, as well as input from consortium partners on planned exploitation activities.

M17 – Preparation of the updated CDEP & Review

M18 – Second version of the CDEP to be published (deliverable).

Timeline above has been followed. Timeline below will be implemented.

M19-M30 - Opportunity for the CDB to provide comments and proposals during this period

M19-M30 - Implementation of Communication and Dissemination Activities

M19-M36 - Work on the Exploitation Strategy

M36 - Third version of the CDEP to be published (deliverable)